

Popular Article

The Role of Nutrition in Canine Performance and Rehabilitation

Dr. Pallabi Das

Assistant Professor, Department of Animal Nutrition, M.B. Veterinary College, Dungarpur, Rajasthan-314001

Introduction

Nutrition plays an integral role in sports performance and rehabilitation. Performance dogs engage in a wide range of pursuits, possibly requiring nutritional adjustments for best performance that center on substrate use. Compared to endurance athletes, sprinting dogs need more carbohydrates as their primary fuel for exercise. These concepts work best when applied by an athlete who is well-trained, fit, and in optimal physical condition, which varies a little depending on the sport. However, many athletes are kept slim to prevent carrying too much weight, regardless of the workload. Clients with performance dogs need to be aware of the risks of vitamin and mineral imbalances caused by common feeding habits that frequently do not include commercial dog food as an element of the ration. Dietary guidelines for nutritional adequacy for wound healing and maintaining lean body mass are frequently used in rehabilitation. Lean body mass and protein consumption are key ideas in the management of obesity, which can also be a part of rehabilitation and gerontology. Long-chain omega-3 fatty acids and other nutraceuticals can be used to treat canine osteoarthritis, a common side effect of many orthopedic operations, by reducing chronic inflammation and improving mobility.

Nutrition for performance Dietary protein - beyond energy

Dogs can produce non-essential amino acids by deamination and carboxylation processes, which transform carbon precursors and necessary amino acids into nonessential amino acids, in addition to the essential amino acids that are provided in the diet. According to the NRC, the minimum amount of protein needed for maintenance is just 20 g/1000 kcal, or 10-12% crude protein in a typical dry commercial product. Protein from food helps maintain healthy levels of total protein, albumin, and red blood cells as well as the integrity of muscles. With training and competition, the hematocrit and serum albumin tend to drop, and these drops seem to be the outcome of overtraining syndrome. The acute phase response, in which the liver alters its protein synthesis profile to include proteins like haptoglobin and C-reactive protein, possibly at the expense of albumin, can be linked to this illness. The plasma volume of the dogs in the protein-rich group increased by 10%, while hematocrit, hemoglobin, total blood volume, and protein consumption all correlated linearly.

Dietary fat and carbohydrate- energy and demands

The proportion of oxygen consumed to CO₂ produced is known as the respiratory quotient (RQ). For the purpose of producing CO₂, predominantly fat is devoured when the RQ is near to 0.7, whereas glucose is consumed when the RQ is close to 1. Protein oxidation is low during the first 20 to 30 minutes of exercise, making it possible to study substrate usage and variations in oxygen demand while feeding various carbohydrate and fat diets. Animals that engage in vigorous exercise for the initial few seconds depend on the phosphocreatine system, which produces ATP by converting inorganic phosphate to ADP. Soon after, glycolysis starts to occur, producing enough energy for standard sprinting or intermediate workout. If glycolysis is sustained, production of pyruvate and eventually lactic acid prevails, resulting in pH alteration and intracellular dysfunction. As long as there is glycogen available for glycogenolysis, pyruvate incorporation into the citric acid cycle (carbohydrate oxidation) turns into a significant source of energy for prolonged exercise (20 to 2 hours). Eventually, if glycogen is depleted during endurance activity, protein oxidation will happen. A dog won't be able to maintain oxygen intake above 50–60% of Vo₂ max once glycogen is depleted. After 30 minutes of exercise, fatty acid oxidation increases and is maintained as the main fuel at an oxygen consumption rate between 30 and 50% of maximal. With about 40–50% of the ME in the diet being easily digested carbs, using carbohydrates as a key nutritional substrate makes sense for sprinting animals like Greyhounds. There are no specific carbohydrate requirements for endurance sled dogs, therefore they may only require less than 15% of the ME in the form of carbs.

Dietary fiber

Whatever its form, dietary fibre causes faecal bulk. This increase in faecal mass has the potential to cause the competitor to urinate inappropriately during competition and to carry more weight than necessary, both of which could be harmful. There are two types of fibre: soluble and insoluble (nonfermentable) (fermentable). When diarrhea is a concern, insoluble fibre produces faecal bulk and serves as a binding agent that can enhance faecal quality. Through villous hypertrophy, soluble fibre has the potential to change the large intestinal microbiota and maybe enhance the absorptive surface of the small and large intestine. This has been used tastefully in canine athletes that get diarrhea from stress. Certain bacterial genera, such as bifidobacterial, lactobacilli, and streptococci, frequently thrive on soluble fibre. To enhance faecal quality and intestine absorption capacities, several enteric formulas of commercial dog food employ trace amounts of gums, soy fibre, fructo-oligosaccharides, other oligosaccharides, and combined insoluble and soluble fibre sources. Since excessive fermentation might lead to worsening faecal quality, the amount of soluble fibre provided is typically less than 2% of the dry matter in the diet.

Electrolytes, minerals, and the canine athlete

Major minerals and trace minerals are two categories of minerals. Since shortages in dogs fed unconventional diets (meat foundation without bone) have been noted, the key minerals are of the utmost

importance. To improve the calcium and phosphorus balance, it is frequently advised to have the bones pulverized into the meat supply if meats are being used. To maintain calcium homeostasis for bone structural integrity as well as the proper cellular signaling and buffering capacities, calcium should be between 0.6 and 1.2% dry matter and similar quantities of phosphorus. Magnesium is also a problem in atypical diets when commercial feed is not used and bone is not a component. When dogs are active, a deficiency may show as hyperextension of the carpus. Other significant mineral deficiencies, such as those in sodium, potassium, and chloride, have never been found in adult working dogs. However, during competitions and simulated endurance races, nonclinical hyponatremia has been seen in endurance Huskies.

When eating commercial dog food, trace mineral intake will rise proportionately. Meat supplements to commercial diets will also somewhat raise trace mineral intake. A clinical shortage in copper, zinc, iron, manganese, iodine, or selenium has not yet been identified in athletic dogs on standard commercial or commercial dog food/meat mix diets. This is probably because most pet diets contain more trace elements than the minimum allowed by AAFCO, and because active dogs eat more than non-active dogs do.

Vitamins/antioxidants and the canine athlete

Vitamins can either be categorized as fat- or water-soluble. As coenzymes and intermediates in the citric acid cycle or as transporters and coenzymes for carbon transfer, water-soluble vitamins play a role in metabolism. These vitamins must be consumed in sufficient amounts for metabolism to occur. Since water-soluble vitamins have wide margins of safety, they are widely commercialized. Although canines may not manufacture as much vitamin C as other species do, dog meals and meats often contain a good amount of this vitamin because it is the most abundant water-soluble antioxidant in the mammalian body. Two to 10 times the minimal required will be found in the majority of commercial pet foods. The margins of safety for fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, and K) are narrower and cause for greater caution. In the digestive tract of healthy dogs, native microorganisms create enough vitamin K. Given the higher energy requirements of athletic dogs and the fact that many commercial dog diets include at least twice as much cholecalciferol than is required, the amount of cholecalciferol consumed is typically appropriate. Tocopherol supplementation is not advised for canine athletes as long as they are receiving enough complete and balanced dog food, but vitamin E supplementation (200–400 IU for a typical athletic 20–40 kg dog) should be taken into consideration for dogs receiving non-traditional diets (primarily meats) to prevent deficiency.

Nutritional strategies and rehabilitation

The control of obesity, maintaining lean body mass (especially for senior rehabilitation patients with sarcopenia), and reducing chronic inflammation linked to orthopedic illness are the three main areas of

concern for canine rehabilitation patients. The precise causes are complex and include overfeeding, inactivity, and the widespread misperception among dog owners regarding what constitutes a healthy bodily condition. An organized rehabilitation exercise routine demonstrates that lean body mass can be maintained even when losing weight. Both strategies have not been proven to enhance weight reduction, however more active dogs can consume more calories while on the weight loss plan, which may increase compliance. better. This seems to be a successful weight loss method for enhancing health.